

**CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ONLINE PURCHASES
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO WOMEN DRESS AND
COSMETICS (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
POLLACHI TALUK)**

Dr. S. Shanmugapriya* & S. Pratheepa**

* Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Commerce, NGM College,
Pollachi, Tamilnadu

** Full Time Research Scholar, PG & Research Department of Commerce, NGM College, Pollachi, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

The customer usage and satisfaction of online purchases with special reference to women dress and cosmetics. The main aim of the study to analyze the women customers satisfaction level in online shopping of women garments and cosmetics. The research study consists of both primary and secondary data. The primary data have been collected with the help of structured questionnaire. Secondary data for the study were collected from the books, journals, research, articles, magazines, report newspaper and websites. The total sample size 120 respondents were selected for the study using. The outcome of the study This study focus to attempt significance on various personal details like age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, area of residence, occupation, type of family, number of members in family, monthly income and customer satisfaction changes according to the advanced technology, fashion and price of the product.

Key Words: Purchase, Online & Customer Satisfaction

Introduction:

Online shopping re also called as e-shopping is a form of electronic commerce authorized consumers to directly buy goods and services from of a seller over the internet using web browsers. The alternative names are: e-web –store, e-shop e-store, online store virtual store etc. The mobile commerce (or m-commerce) describes purchasing from an online retailer's mobile optimized online site or app., English entrepreneur Michael Aldrich invented online shopping in 1979. His system connected a modified domestic TV to a real – time transaction processing computer via a domestic telephone line. In March 1980 he went on to launch region's office revaluation, which authorized consumers, customer, suppliers, distributors, agents, and services companies to be connected on –line to the corporate systems and allow business transactions to be completed electronically in real-time. Online shopping portals are witnessing a whopping 200% growth in the sale of electronic items every year. This is driven by the demands like mobile phones, iPods and MP3 players not only from metros but also from small cities. Some online shopping portals in India are www. homeshop18.com, www.flipkart.com www.myntra.com American online retail giant amazon.com has also made an entry into the Indian market in 2012 with jungle.com, an online shopping site powered by the \$ 48 billion company.

Review of Literature:

Saranya. W and P. Palanivelu (2015). In "a study on customer preference and satisfaction towards online shopping on flip kart in Coimbatore district". In their study, they tried to analyze customer preference on flip kart shopping and to assess their satisfaction level towards flip kart and type of product preferred by consumer and their payment method. The finding was most number of females are using online shopping when they promotes offers discount for products. Mostly the respondents are shopping when offers and discounts this was the final result of the study.

K. Brinda Devi, Dr. S. Saravanan (2015). In "A study on online buying behaviors with special reference to Coimbatore city". The main objective of the study is to discover the order of preference given by the online buyer for different online website and assess the most frequently buying product through online shopping. Online consumer trends to be better educated higher computer literacy makes internet shopping smarts. Their awareness about the internet also makes them better positioned to identify and take decision for products and services.

P. Priyanga, Dr. R. Krishnaveni, (2013). In "study on perception of women consumer towards branded cosmetics in Nagapattinam district." In this study they analyzed the demographic profile of the cosmetics using consumer and to find out the most preferred type of cosmetic and factors influencing to purchase and to give some suggestion for the betterment. Price and Brand image of products are two majority elected features affecting their preference for selecting a particular brand. Consumer trend to use latest type of cosmetics for many reasons against traditional ones there is a need for organization to first conduct extensive research in

effectively understanding the preference behavior of consumers, there is a need to understand the important roles of each cosmetic product. Thus cosmetic firms should concentrate on quality control measures.

L. I. M. Ying San, T. E. O. Yuan Sim, (2012). In “cosmetic product a study of Malaysian women shoppers in cyberspace” they tried to found it attitude and behavior of the women shopper in cyberspace. This study, result showed that there was a relationship between consumer online shopping experience and intention to purchase online .it holds the highest importance in influencing intention to purchase online. Therefore, it is demonstrated by past research findings stated that consumer online shopping experiences have a direct impact on intention to purchase online.

Statement of the Problem:

To shop online becomes an alternative for the woman consumer since it is more comfortable than conventional shopping. The purpose of the dissertation was to examine if there is any particular factors that influence the online shopping. This research is primarily in order to identify and get insight of women consumer satisfaction in online shopping, to identify the factors that affect the women satisfaction and difficulty faced at the time returning products that are purchased through online.

Objective of the Study:

To find out the solution for the above problems the present study has been undertaken with the following objectives.

- ✓ To know the personal profile and details about woman’s respondents.
- ✓ To identify the customer usage of online shopping websites.
- ✓ To analyze the women customers satisfaction level in online shopping of women garments and cosmetics.

Research Methodology:

The present study is mainly based on primary data. Data is collected by distributing the questionnaire to the customers residing in Pollachi taluk. The questionnaire contains question relating to the personal profile of the customer, usage and satisfaction of online shopping. Necessary guidance was given to the respondents for filling up the questionnaire.

Scope of the Study:

The critical importance of the customer satisfaction in online shopping stores has been recognized in academic research and its literature, in particular. However, studies in this area remain broad and to some extent fragmented. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to test empirically the integrated model of the customer satisfaction. This study on 120 questionnaire survey in Pollachi taluk.

Sampling:

The study is concerned with women customer in online shopping usage of the total 130 questionnaire issued 120 questionnaire are collected and are taken for analysis because of in completed information found in the 10questionnaire.the convenient sampling method is adopted to select the sample customers.

Frame Work of Analysis:

The primary data collected were reformulated and consolidated into master table. Simple percentage and chi- square test are applied to process the data and draw inferences. Inferences have been made by comparing the collected chi – square value with the respected table value. The results have been tested at one and five percentage level.

Analysis and Interpretation:

An attempt has been to identify the work of the socio-economic profile of the respondents has been evaluated by using simple percentage analysis and the results are summarized in the following table shown bellow.

Table 1: Socio – Economic Profile

Particular		No. of Respondents	Percent
Area of residence	Rural	75	62.5
	Urban	45	37.5
Age	Below 20years	21	17.5
	21 – 30years	46	38.33
	31 -45years	37	30.33
	Above 45 years	13	13.33
Marital status	Married	54	45
	Unmarried	66	55
Educational qualification	Illiterate	6	5
	SSLC/HSC	14	11.67
	UG	23	19.17
	PG	44	36.67
	Professional	12	10

	M.Phil/Ph.D	11	8.33
	Diploma	10	8.33
Occupation	Agriculturist	17	14.18
	Govt./Pvt- employee	24	20.00
	Professional	29	24.18
	Business/entrepreneurs	5	4.18
	Home maker	22	18.33
	Retired person	2	1.68
	Other	20	16.68
	Nature of family	Joint	46
Nuclear		74	61.68
No. of members in the family	2	7	5.83
	3	35	29.17
	4	38	31.67
	Above 4	40	33.33
No. of earning members in the family	1	42	35
	2	68	56.68
	3	7	5.83
	Above 3	3	2.5
Monthly income (self) (in Rs.)	Below 10,000	32	26.67
	10,001 - 20,000	43	35.83
	20,001 - 40,000	20	16.67
	Above 40,000	14	11.67
Annual income (family) (in Rs)	Below 1,00,000	54	45
	1,00,001 - 2,00,000	32	26.67
	2,00,001 – 4,00,000	25	20.83
	Above 4,00,001	9	7.05

Source: Primary Data

From the above table 62.5 respondents belong to the rural area, 38.33 percent of the respondents belongs to the age group between 21- 30 years, 55 percent of the respondents belongs to the married, 36.67 percent of the respondents belongs to the PG, 24.18 percent of the respondents belongs to the professional, 61.68 percent of the respondents belongs to the nuclear family, 33.33 percent of the respondents belongs to the above 4 family members, 56.68 percent of the respondents belongs to the 2 family members earning, 35.83 percent of the respondents belongs to the rs.10001- rs.20000 monthly income, 26.67 percent of the respondents belongs to the Rs.100000- Rs. 200000.

Chi-Square Analysis:

The chi-square test is an important test among the several statistical techniques employed for analyzing the significance among variables. Here the independent variables namely age, residence, educational qualification, monthly income level, occupation has been tested for their significations with the dependent variable investment in commodities

Table 2: Selected Variable and Level of Satisfaction on Online Shopping

Variables	Chi – Square Value	D.F	Table Value 5 Percent Level
Area of residence	2.090*	2	5.991
Age	9.93*	6	12.592
Marital status	3.325*	2	5.991
Educational qualification	35.201*	14	23.68
Occupation	22.947*	12	21.026
Nature of family	3.258*	2	5.991
No. of members in the family	4.340*	6	12.592
No. of earning members in the family	4.060*	6	12.592
Monthly income (self) (in Rs.)	5.439*	8	15.507

The above table 2 discloses that out the total eight variables selected, six variables are found to be significant with the consumer's level of satisfaction on online shopping. Of them six variables namely area of residence, gender, marital status, types of the family, no of members in the family, no of earning members in the family, monthly income of the family are significantly associated with the consumers level of satisfaction at the five per cent level.

Findings:

Simple Percentage: The major finding of the study are summarized as follows, there are

- ✓ Majority of the respondents are residing in the rural area.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are in the age group between 21 -30 years.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are married.
- ✓ Educational qualifications of most of respondents are post graduation.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are professional.
- ✓ Monthly income of the respondents is up to Rs.10,001- 20,000.
- ✓ 61 per cent of the respondents belong to the nuclear family.
- ✓ Most of the respondents have four members their family.
- ✓ 56 per cent of the respondents have more the two earning members in their family.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Extra charges and rates should be reduced in online shopping.
- ✓ The online shoppers may give more advertisement about the product, price details etc.,
- ✓ The online shoppers create more confidence that they supply only quality of product, affordable price, time of delivery etc,
- ✓ Online shoppers may give more offers should be provided about the women dress and cosmetics.
- ✓ The online shopper may buy to overcome the problems given by the various consumers.

Conclusion:

Online shopping is very common outside Indian but it is growing on Indian market. In the volatile world of e-commerce, it is particularly to understand the consumer and the values that lead to their satisfaction. Successful e-commerce sites need to exhibit more qualities than just good size design and security. While browsing a site online consumer encounter a multitude of factors simultaneously that influence their purchasing decision. This study focus to attempt significance on various personal details like age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, area of residence, occupation, type of family, number of members in family, monthly income and customer satisfaction changes according to the advanced technology, fashion and price of the product.

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